

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B443
 Date: 30 Apr 2009
 Take Off: 10:59:43Z
 Landing: 16:02:33Z
 Flight Time 5h 02m 40s

Campaign: MEVEX Maritime Flight 5
Operating Area: Oman

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Pollard	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / AVAPS	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
8	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	
10	Wet Neph / CVI / IIR	Andy Wilson	Met Office	
11	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office	
12	Mission Scientist 2	Jon Taylor	Met Office	
13	Mini-LIDAR	Joss Kent	Met Office	
14	Observer	Dave Membury	Met Office	
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Brief	Sortie brief yet to be added
Mission Scientist 1	Mission Scientist 1 log not passed to FAAM for inclusion
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by ???
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
Cloud Physics	Log not passed to folder creator
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Neph	No log passed to FAAM yet
CVI	No log passed to FAAM yet
SWS	No log passed to FAAM yet
Mini-Lidar	No log passed to FAAM yet
IIR	No IIR log is provided for the Flight Folder

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	31 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_072302_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_082231_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_063237_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_072257_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_082228_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_053234_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_063234_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_072254_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_082226_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_053237_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_053758_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_063758_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_072305_1hz.avi

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B443
 Date: 30/04/2009
 Project: MEVEX
 Location: Oman

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
104902		Start-Up	0.23 kft	266	
105301		taxy	0.23 kft	266	
105431		ASP	0.23 kft	266	open
105953		T/O	0.0 kft	127	
111204		JW	kft	127	zero
112011		TWC	23.0 kft	089	evap 2
112721		JW	23.0 kft	089	zero
112730		Heimann	23.0 kft	090	cal
113300	115122	Profile 1	23.0 - 6.2 kft	090	
114401		TWC	12.9 kft	110	evap2
115323	115917	Profile 1	6.2 - 3.2 kft	276	
120112		Heimann	3.3 kft	103	cal
120214	120627	Run 1.1	3.2 kft	359	
120823	121739	Run 1.2	3.2 kft	257	
121746	122043	Profile 2	3.1 - 0.83 kft	098	
122043	122926	Run 2.1	0.83 - 0.71 kft	014	
122442		Heimann	0.74 kft	356	cal
122938	123505	Run 2.2	0.76 - 0.74 kft	182	
123511	123722	Profile 3	0.80 - 3.1 kft	196	
124002	125004	Run 3.1	3.1 kft	021	
125906	130615	Run 3.2	3.1 kft	210	
130621	130829	Profile 4	3.2 - 5.1 kft	181	
131022	132016	Run 4.1	5.1 kft	020	
131707		Heimann	5.1 kft	357	cal
132025	132820	Run 4.2	5.1 kft	201	
132830	133245	Profile 5	5.0 - 3.1 kft	180	
133645	134311	Run 5.1	3.1 kft	234	
134450	135329	Run 5.2	3.2 kft	087	
135335	135632	Profile 6	3.1 - 1.2 kft	274	
135645	140411	Run 6.1	1.1 kft	268	
140407		Heimann	1.1 kft	053	cal
135930		Heimann			cal
140431	141207	Run 6.2	1.1 kft	095	
141216	142104	Run 6.3	1.1 kft	280	
142113	143424	Run 6.4	1.1 kft	100	
143018		JW	1.1 kft	164	zero
143059		Heimann	1.1 kft	251	cal
143434	144045	Run 6.5	1.1 kft	270	
144059	144148	Profile 7.1	1.0 - 0.60 kft	257	sawtooth
144148	144318	Profile 7.2	0.60 - 1.3 kft	253	
144318	144454	Profile 7.3	1.3 - 0.58 kft	255	

144454	144611	Profile 7.4	0.58 - 1.1 kft	254 sawtooth end
144746	145618	Run 7.1	1.1 kft	079
145625	150321	Run 7.2	1.1 kft	280
145710		Heimann	1.1 kft	283 cal
150329	150739	Run 7.3	1.1 kft	106
150749	151105	Run 7.4	1.1 kft	261
152009		Sonde 01	20.0 kft	299
160233		Land	0.21 kft	266 Muscat
160500		ASP	0.21 kft	266 close
160838		Shutdown	0.21 kft	266 23 35.36N 58 17.66E

B443 10:22:04-16:10:08

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 462 Date 30 APR 09 Name Jon Taylor Page 1 of 4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
114720					Passed over runway at 9000ft she was to part. XXXXXXXXXX XXXXXXXXXX XXXXXXXXXX
113300	P1	F230W	220		
115222	P1	6000ft			Intercept Profile P1 at 6000ft
					Elevated radar duct at 12,500ft
115326	P1	6000ft	280		Rollout P1 ↓ to 3000ft.
115917	P1	3000ft	260		End of P1
120214	RI-1	3000ft			Start Run 1:1 to pass over ship Missed ship was were target to left IRI = MISS. wind 008 / 315°
120627	RI-1	3000ft		22°48'N 62°24'E	End RI-1
120823	RI-2	3000ft	240		RI-2 12nm out XXXXXXXXXX IRI + VIS camera = MISS. Flying above of tanker saw wake
121746	RI-2 + ST P2			22°18'N 62°12'E	End RI-2 ↓ to 6000ft
122043	RI-2:1	600ft			Start Run 2:1 IRI = ✓. slash attack. PCASP low ~ 800 → 1000/10

Mission Scientist's Log

MEVEX

Flight No B 443 Date 30 APR 09 Name Jon Taylor Page 2 of 4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
122938	R2.2	600ft			Run 2.2
					missed ship on missed ship on conv
123505	R2.2/P3	600ft			End R2.2 and climb to 3000ft
123700	P3	3000ft			Level at 3000ft End P3
124002	R3.1	3000ft	vble		St Run 3.1 Range 16km IRL = hit. on wide angle camera.
125004	R3.1	3000ft	variable		End Run 3.1
125906	3.2	3000ft	211		st Run 3.2 towards ship
130000					missed ship on
130615	R3.2/P4	3000ft	181		End of Run + climb to 5000ft
131022	R4.1	5000ft	026		St Run 4.1 range 16km mid 007 / 280° T = 26.4 Td = -1.12
132025	R4.2	5000ft	202		Run 4.2 2500ft to cross ship.
133645	R5.1	3000ft	234		Run 5.1 3000ft missed ship on
134311	R5.1	3000ft	253	22°18'W 61°54'E	End Run 5.1
134650	R5.2	3000ft	100		Run 5.2 3000ft to cross ship.
135335	P6	3000ft	1000ft		P2 descend to 1000ft.
135645	R6.1	1000ft	262		Run 6.1 + end P6. to pass ship missed ship on
135918	= 7 time graphics				+ in wide angle camera.

Mission Scientist's Log

MISS SCI 2

Flight No B. 443 Date 30 APR 109 Name Jon Taylor Page 3 of 4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
140411	R6.1	1000ft			End R6.1
140431	R6.2	1000ft	073		St Run 6.2 T=35.12 Td=28.
					Saw wake in narrow, ship missed in wake due to narrow gap (MCS)
					End Run 6.2
141216		1000ft	282		St Run 6.3
141717					Sun has set.
141630.					Ship wake in narrow, ship is in wide angle
142113		1000ft			End Run 6.3 + start 6.4
					LW good capture
					MW camera is banded out.
					depth = -2.42 w/m ²
					Red = 25.77 w/m ² .
143634	R6.5	1000ft			End Run 6.4 St Run 6.5 over ship
143956.					
144054 → 144148			7.1	On down	Radar duct at 1.1 to 600ft
144148 → 144318			7.2	On climb	no duct
144318 → 144454			7.3	on descent	no duct
144454 → 144611			7.4	Ascent	no duct.
144746	R7.1	1000ft.			1000ft pass over ship run
145218					LWR IRC got in narrow for ast in MWIR due to data loss. SST is 28°C

B443-#mevexViRClog

```
*** Opened channel log for #mevex at 30/04/2009 11:39:27
[2009/04/30 11:39] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/30 11:39] [FAAMOpsDetach] Hi James, its working now!!
[2009/04/30 11:39] [FAAMOpsDetach] Thank You
[2009/04/30 11:41] <james> Great. Sorry about the hitch...
[2009/04/30 11:42] [FAAMOpsDetach] No worries. We can't really complain as you are doing us a
    favour.
[2009/04/30 11:45] <james> How's it going out there?
[2009/04/30 11:54] [FAAMOpsDetach] It was very hectic for the first week (as normal) but it has
    settled down now. By the end of play tomorrow we
[2009/04/30 11:54] [FAAMOpsDetach] will have flown 7 flights in 6 days. ..a bit better than the
    cranfield hit rate
[2009/04/30 11:58] *** FAAM_flt_man (~GLUXE@203.38.13.32) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/30 11:58] [FAAMOpsDetach] hello
[2009/04/30 11:58] <FAAM_flt_man> wocha
[2009/04/30 12:03] [FAAMOpsDetach] trying to make progress with flinux, unsuccessfully
[2009/04/30 12:08] <FAAM_flt_man> I think the key is connecting to the web
[2009/04/30 12:13] [FAAMOpsDetach] trouble is the key has snapped off in the lock
[2009/04/30 12:13] [FAAMOpsDetach] Is the spotter working now?
[2009/04/30 12:14] <FAAM_flt_man> missed the ship all runs so far. Spotter intermittent.
[2009/04/30 12:18] [FAAMOpsDetach] Dave and Doug have gone out to the shops for the video bits
[2009/04/30 12:18] <FAAM_flt_man> boys!
[2009/04/30 12:29] [FAAMOpsDetach] I've just forwarded an email to the yahoo account from Paul
    Barrett, for James ref CVI CPC. Can you print it out and pass it on please?
[2009/04/30 12:30] [FAAMOpsDetach] Via the outlook express icon on the desktop
[2009/04/30 12:31] <FAAM_flt_man> 10:4 good biddie
[2009/04/30 13:00] <FAAM_flt_man> !!!!posn rep has snuck through
[2009/04/30 13:00] *** FAAM_flt_man (~GLUXE@203.38.13.32) has quit IRC
[2009/04/30 13:13] *** FAAM_flt_man (~GLUXE@203.38.13.32) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/30 13:13] [FAAMOpsDetach] all okay?
[2009/04/30 13:14] [FAAMOpsDetach] i'm on the blower to Dave T
[2009/04/30 13:15] [FAAMOpsDetach] got the idl license running, now trying the network bit
[2009/04/30 13:15] <FAAM_flt_man> yes, all ok. Better success with camera
[2009/04/30 13:15] <FAAM_flt_man> Capt Clivir?
[2009/04/30 13:24] *** james (~james@goliath2.seaes.manchester.ac.uk) has quit IRC [Remote host
    closed the connection]
[2009/04/30 13:25] [FAAMOpsDetach] is the camera now squint-free?
[2009/04/30 13:27] <FAAM_flt_man> no, but the pilots's have got the right idea now, doing runs at a
    20deg bearing to the ship to maximise the chance of success
[2009/04/30 13:59] [FAAMOpsDetach] internet working!!!!!!
[2009/04/30 13:59] [FAAMOpsDetach] Dave saves the day again!!!!
[2009/04/30 14:05] <FAAM_flt_man> Beau-dacious!
[2009/04/30 14:11] [FAAMOpsDetach] Captainette Clivir
[2009/04/30 14:18] <FAAM_flt_man> so a whole evening of processing 4 motre
[2009/04/30 14:20] *** FAAM_flt_man (~GLUXE@203.38.13.32) has quit IRC [Read error: Connection
    reset by peer]
[2009/04/30 14:20] [FAAMOpsDetach] do you have an updated eta?
[2009/04/30 14:33] *** FAAM_flt_man (~GLUXE@203.52.191.244) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/30 14:33] <FAAM_flt_man> um big drop out
[2009/04/30 14:34] [FAAMOpsDetach] do you have a refreshed eta?
[2009/04/30 14:35] [FAAMOpsDetach] I am going to go for tea soon, as I didn't have lunch
[2009/04/30 14:35] <FAAM_flt_man> nope. Still working the ship, 22 24N 62 6 E
[2009/04/30 14:35] [FAAMOpsDetach] Okay
[2009/04/30 14:36] [FAAMOpsDetach] Doug is about to join virc so he will keep a watching eye on
    things while I go a la carte daft
[2009/04/30 14:37] <FAAM_flt_man> ok.
[2009/04/30 14:38] [FAAMOpsDetach] tattie bye
*** Closed channel log for #mevex at 30/04/2009 14:38:07
*** Opened channel log for #MEVEX at 30/04/2009 15:46:20
[2009/04/30 15:46] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #MEVEX
[2009/04/30 16:18] *** FAAMOpsDoug (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has quit IRC
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Flight:

B443

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

ARIES flight log

Flight: B443

page 1 of 1

Date: 30/04/09

Operator(s): S. Rogers

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NEVER: Ship wake

Scans: either "[IGMs][co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
~1100	TAKE OFF						ARIES still ok after the morning's B442.
11 16 40	FL230	cal	CH	0	81	41	
11 18 55		120x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith Ci above ✓
11 20 05		N3min	N	0	81	41	Nadir 3min
12 02 20	^{R11} 3000'	N3min	N	0	81	41	Nadir 3min
12 08 17	^{R12}	Z3min	Z	0	81	42	Zenith 3min
12 20 48	600'	N3min	N	0	81	42	Nadir (turn of way out)
12 29 28	"	Z3min	Z	0	81	45	Zenith. CBB flanking at ambient?
12 40 07	3000'	N3min	N	0	81	46	Nadir. Window 38C mirror 40C
12 59 06	"	Z3min	Z	0	81	46	Zenith
13 06 26	^{R14} ↑	cal	CH	0	81	46	CH cal.
13 10 27	5000'	N3min	N	0	81	45	Nadir
13 20 24	"	Z3min	Z	0	81	44	Zenith
13 28 40	↓	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal
13 36 48	^{R15} 3000'	N3min	N	0	81	42	Nadir
13 44 50	"	Z3min	Z	0	81	43	Zenith
13 53	↓	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal
13 55 45	↓ 1000'	N3min	N	0	81	44	Nadir 3min Note CBB getting towards
14 04 45	"	Z3min	Z	0	81	46	Zenith
14 12 14	"	N3min	N	0	81	47	Nadir
14 21 09	"	Z3min	Z	0	81	47	Zenith
14 30 56	"	N3min	N	0	81	49	Nadir When CBB ≥ 50C it is displayed as 100C !!!
14 47 40	1000'	N3min	N	0	81	50	End 1441
14 56 23	"	Z3min	Z	0	81	50	Zenith
15 03 30	"	N3min	N	0	81	50	Nadir. (cal at crucial moment!)
							RE-01511 Window 43C mirror 40C
15 18 22	FL200	N3min	N	0	81	47	Nadir 3min + Sonda

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	30/4/09	Flight	B443	log pages
Operator(s)	J Bowles		Campaign	MEVEX		
Departure	Muscat		Arrival	Muscat		

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						Y
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on	at time					
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	54°C	Ch	58°C	Ch18	40°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time					09:51
Initial target temperatures	Hot	326	Cold	312		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	10:48:50		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.56	Cold	315.68	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	41.1	32.0	37.3	39.8	40.6	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again	at time					

Flight B443 15:20:58

Heading 298 deg Speed 291 knots Height 20.0kft Press 465mb

Lat 22°42.0'N Long 60°54.0'E Wind 8 ms-1/ 309 deg

Temp -12.54C Dewpoint -40.15C

From 14:29:00 to now

Current values
PRESSURE HEIGHT 20 Kft
REFRACTMTY 139.68 Munits
 All

Flight B443 15:20:46

Heading 298 deg Speed 291 knots Height 20.0kft Press 465mb

Lat 22°42.0'N Long 61°0.0'E Wind 8 ms-1/ 309 deg

Temp -12.53C Dewpoint -39.69C

From 15:11:00 to now

Current values			
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	20.01	Kft
++++	NEPH BLUE SP	5.74	m-1
++++	NEPH GREEN SP	2.87	m-1
++++	NEPH RED SP	3.44	m-1

Flight B443 11:59:27

Heading 280 deg Speed 245 knots Height 3.1kft Press 901mb

Lat 22°36.0'N Long 62°12.0'E Wind 9 ms-1/ 312 deg

Temp 30.5C Dewpoint 0.97C

From 11:33:00 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	901.88	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	30.51	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	0.98	deg C

Flight B443 11:59:20

Heading 280 deg Speed 248 knots Height 3.2kft Press 901mb

Lat 22°36.0'N Long 62°12.0'E Wind 8 ms-1/ 312 deg

Temp 30.39C Dewpoint 0.95C

From 11:33:00 to now

Current values				
.....	PRESSURE HEIGHT	3.2	Kft	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
.....	NEPH BLUE SP	100.72	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
.....	NEPH GREEN SP	96.8	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
.....	NEPH RED SP	91.78	m-1	<input type="radio"/>

D20090430_152012.1 082119296 none, none

